

Microspectrophotometric determination of thorium(IV) and uranium(VI) with methylthymol blue

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Manuscript received 13 April 2004, revised 19 May 2005, accepted 28 June 2005

Attempts have been made to improve the sensitivity of complexation reactions of Th^{IV} and U^{VI} with methylthymol blue (MTB) in presence of cationic surfactant cetyldimethylethylammonium bromide (CDEAB). The marked bathochromic shift in λ_{max} , considerable increase in sensitivity and extreme stability of these ternary complexes in presence of CDEAB were found to be useful in microdetermination of metal ions under study. The composition and values of conditional formation constants have been evaluated in presence of CDEAB and various analytical parameters, viz. conformity to Beer's law, photometric ranges, Sandell's sensitivity and molar absorptivity have been studied.

Attempts have been made to improve the sensitivity of some reagents for the microdetermination of rare earths using cetyltrimethylammonium bromide and cetylpyridinium bromide¹. The ternary complexes of Ga^{III} , Pb^{IV} ² and Fe^{III} ³ with pyrocatechol violet in presence of some cationic surfactants have been studied earlier. Methylthymol blue (MTB) was used for the determination of Th^{IV} ⁴ and U^{VI} ⁵ using cetyldimethylethylammonium bromide (CDEAB). The present investigation describes the systematic study on the use of methylthymol blue as sensitive microspectrophotometric reagent for Th^{IV} and U^{VI} ions.

Results and discussion

Absorption spectra of MTB : The absorption spectra of MTB solution show characteristic λ_{max} in alkaline medium at 630 nm and in acidic medium 430 nm. On addition of CDEAB in acidic medium the absorbance decreases with the appearance of new peak at 450 nm causing a colour change blue to pale gray and in more dilute solution almost colourless. This colour change at high pH value has been achieved in acidic medium due to early dissociation of protons in acidic medium in presence of CDEAB⁶. This decolourisation might be attributed due to interaction between anionic dye and cationic surfactant.

Effect of CDEAB on MTB : The maximum decolourising effect on MTB in presence of CDEAB has been observed in alkaline medium at 9.5 pH showing minimal ratio 1 : 3 at 630 nm. Therefore the tentative composition of so called "Dye-Surfactant" complex may be represented

as $\text{MTB}(\text{CDEAB})_3$. The direct proof of this complex formation could not be collected in present investigation as all the attempt have been failed to isolate it. The effect caused by addition of CDEAB on the nature of the absorbance spectra of MTB changes in presence of higher amount of mineral salts. The maximum increase in absorbance was caused by the addition of NO_3^- ions, whereas in case of Cl^- and SO_4^{2-} , the effect observed on the absorbance was comparatively less. The difference in action of particular cation was virtually negligible. Similar results were obtained at pH 6.5 and 6.8 where the further complexation in presence of CDEAB have been studied but the effect observed was a less pronounced.

Complex formation with Th^{IV} and U^{VI} : Fig. 1 shows the comparative absorption spectra at pH 6.8. Curve A is absorption spectrum of MTB alone showing λ_{max} 430 nm and B for MTB in presence of CDEAB with λ_{max} 450 nm. Curve C is for MTB- Th^{IV} complex at pH 4.5 having λ_{max} 430 nm indicating the formation of weak binary complex and curve D for Th^{IV} -MTB-CDEAB complex at λ_{max} 500 nm indicating formation of strong ternary complex showing a bathochromic shift of 70 nm.

The absorption spectra of MTB and U^{VI} shows λ_{max} at 430 nm indicating very poor complexation which is shifted to 525 nm in presence of CDEAB owing to the formation of strong ternary complex, showing a bathochromic shift of 95 nm with increase in absorbance.

However strong complexation in presence of CDEAB with a large bathochromic shift of ternary complexes which appeared to be convenient to study the analytical applica-

Fig. 1. Spectra at pH 6.8.

tions further. As the modified MTB reagent has considerable absorbance value at λ_{\max} of the ternary complex, further studies have been made at pH 6.8 at 520 nm for Th^{IV} and pH 6.5 at 550 nm for U^{VI} complex where maximum difference in absorbance between the reagent and ternary complex is observed. The interfering hydrolysis of the polyvalent metal ions in the weakly acidic medium has been suppressed due to increase in the stability of the complexes in presence of CDEAB.

Composition and conditional formation constant: The composition and stability of these complexes in absence and presence of CDEAB have been studied by both mole ratio and Job's method of continuous variation. Both methods indicate the ratio of 1 : 2 as metal : MTB. Thus the composition of the complexes may be formulated as $\text{M}[\text{MTB}(\text{CDEAB})_3]_2$, as three cationic surfactant ions are associated with reagent at the pH of study. The values of $\log K$ evaluated by Job's method are shown in Table 1 which indicate that the ternary complexes are more stabilized.

Effect of time, temperature and reagent concentration: The maximum colour development was observed after 30 minutes in absence and after 15 minutes in presence of CDEAB on addition of metal ions. 2.0 and 1.5 fold excess of MTB is required in absence and in pres-

Table 1. Parameter for analytical applications of the ternary complexes

Parameters	Thorium	Uranium
pH of study	6.8	6.5
λ_{\max} of the binary complex (nm)	430	430
λ_{\max} of the ternary complex (nm)	500	525
Bathochromic shift (nm)	70	95
λ_{\max} of study (nm)	520	550
Metal : [Reagent : CDEAB]	[1(1 : 3) ₂]	[1(1 : 3) ₂]
pH range of stability	3.0–6.8	3.0–6.8
$\log K$ value	9.0745	8.3649
Beer's law range (ppm)	0.23–1.16	0.24–1.43
Effective photometric range (ppm)	0.35–0.93	0.36–1.19
Molar absorptivity ($\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$)	45000	42500
Sandell's sensitivity ($\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$)	0.002	0.0018

ence of CDEAB respectively for full colour development. No effect of temperature is observed on the colour intensity in the range 20 to 60°C.

Analytical applications of the ternary complexes :

A large bathochromic shift, considerable increase in the absorbance values and comparatively less absorbance of MTB resulting into the formation of deeply coloured ternary complexes with higher molar absorptivity and the sensitivity in wider pH range suggests a very useful application of these colour reactions in microspectrophotometric determination of metal ions under study. A systematic investigation of various characteristic properties have been presented in Table 1 and is discussed below.

Beer's law and photometric ranges: The complex formation of Th^{IV} with MTB has been studied earlier in the pH range 4.0–5.0 with λ_{\max} in the range 570–595 nm for the determination of 1–8 mg/ml of Th^{IV} and in the pH range 9.0–10.0 at λ_{\max} 535 nm for the determination of 0.5–2.8 ppm of Th^{IV} by Adams with varying molar absorptivity^{4,7}. Earlier Th^{IV} has been reported to follow the Beer's law 0.3–3 ppm at 590 nm as ternary complex with MTB and diphenylguanidine, with xylenol orange and diphenylguanidine to detect 0.15–0.8 ppm at pH 3.0 at λ_{\max} 578 nm^{8,9}. Similarly U^{VI} has also been detected as ternary complex with chromeazurol-S and various cationic detergents used to detect 0.09–2.29 ppm of U^{VI} ¹⁰ and at pH 6.7 to read the complex at 510 nm for determination of 10–94 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ of U^{VI} ⁵.

In present study, the linearity between the absorbance vs [metal ion] was tested by taking 5 ml of $4 \times 10^{-4} M$

MTB, 10 ml of 10^{-3} M CDEAB and adding varying amount of 4×10^{-4} M metal ion in 50 ml of volumetric flask. The range of adherence to Beer's law was found to be 0.23–1.16 ppm for Th^{IV} and 0.24–1.43 ppm for U^{VI} in presence of CDEAB. The effective range for the photometric determination was found to be 0.35–0.93 ppm for Th^{IV} and 0.36–1.19 ppm for U^{VI}. The values of Sandell's sensitivity and molar absorptivity are reported in Table 1.

The present values of photometric ranges are in well agreement with the values reported earlier for Th^{IV} 4,7-9 and for U^{VI} 5,10 and speak themselves about the use of micelle forming cationic CDEAB in present investigation when metal ions are present in extremely low concentration.

Effect of foreign ions : The method suffers from lack of specificity but the interference are not too many. The determination is possible in absence of Sc³⁺, Ln³⁺, Be²⁺ and In³⁺. The ions like Co²⁺, Ni²⁺, Cu²⁺, Zn²⁺, Fe³⁺, Cd²⁺, Ag⁺ etc. can be masked by adding suitable concentration of cyanide ions, anions like phosphate, tartrate, oxalate, citrate and sulphate strongly interfere. However, Cl⁻, Br⁻ and NO₃⁻ do not interfere.

Procedure for micro determination : Adjust the pH of an aliquot of solution containing 15–60 mg of metal ion to 6.8 for Th^{IV} and 6.5 for U^{VI}. Add 3 ml of modified MTB reagent of the same pH (prepared by taking 2 ml of 10^{-3} M MTB containing 1 ml of 10^{-2} M CDEAB) is added. Make up the volume to 50 ml with distilled water of the same pH. Mix well and allow it to stand for 15 min to attend complete equilibria. Measure the absorbance of solution at 520 nm for Th^{IV} and at 550 nm for U^{VI} against reagent blank. The amount of metal ions present in the sample solution can be evaluated by comparing this absorbance from calibration curve obtained under similar condition. The results of ten determination of 46.40 µg/50 ml of Th^{IV} and 47.40 µg/50 ml of U^{VI} showed standard average deviation of 0.042 and 0.085 respectively.

Conclusion :

Thus the reagent reported in the presence of surfactant CDEAB can be used as one of the most sensitive reagent for the spectrophotometric analysis of Th^{IV} and U^{VI} with accurate and consistently reproducible results when present in extremely small concentration. The increased stability has been achieved in presence of surfactant corresponding to a ternary complexation which is adequate for the analytical purposes. The developed pro-

cedure appeared to be quite sensitive, precise and reproducible. The commercial exploitation of these reactions need further investigation.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of analytical grade. MTB used as its tetrasodium monohydrate salt and CDEAB was supplied by Sigma and Aldrich chemical company, USA, respectively. And its purity was estimated by the argentometric titration for the determination of bromide ion content⁶. The thorium nitrate and uranyl acetate of A.R. grade were supplied by B.D.H., England. The stock solutions of MTB, CDEAB and metal ions were prepared of strength 1.0×10^{-2} M and subsequently diluted with double distilled water.

The pH values of these solutions were adjusted with a Elico (digital) model L1-120 pH meter. Standard HCl and NaOH solutions were used for the adjustment of desired pH of the solutions. A Beckman Model-B spectrophotometer was used for the measurement of the absorbance with glass cuvettes of lightpath 10 mm. All the experiments were carried out at room temperature of $30 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$. The CDEAB solution was first added to MTB solution and was kept to equilibrate for half an hour. The metal ion solution was then added to dye surfactant solution and again kept for half an hour to reach complete equilibrium. This order of mixing the solutions was maintained.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the Director, Laxminarayan Institute of Technology, Nagpur University, Nagpur for providing the necessary facilities and encouragement.

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